

Sequential oscillations in B-Z oscillating system with vanillin as substrate

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Sequential oscillations have been observed in B-Z oscillating system containing vanillin as a single substrate as also along with acetone. Ferroin and Mn^{II} ions have been used as catalysts both separately and in combination. Only Mn^{II} ions have been found to be suitable for inducing second phase oscillations. Oscillation parameters have been determined potentiometrically. The effects of variations in the concentrations of acid, acetone and vanillin have been investigated. The mechanism of the reaction has been discussed. It is most likely that sequential oscillations are due to vanillin and its oxidation/bromination products.

Chemical oscillation has been studied extensively¹. Belousov-Zhabotinsky oscillating reaction is perhaps the most widely investigated reaction both in batch and CSTR mode. Both temporal and spatial studies have been made. Different substrates (single or mixed) have been used in place of malonic or citric acid. In the present studies vanillin has been used as substrate both in presence and absence of acetone as also in presence and absence of catalyst. Vanillin, however, has been used earlier only by a few workers². A detailed study has been made here with this substrate and sequential oscillations³ have been observed. After a few oscillations, a nonoscillatory period followed and after that a second series of oscillations appeared. The system finally bifurcated to a stable branch. Oscillation characteristics have been ascertained from potentiometric traces. The concentrations of acid (H_2SO_4), acetone and vanillin have been varied and the effects on the oscillation parameters noted. A few high frequency first phase oscillations occurred even in the absence of a catalyst. Mn^{II} ions induced second phase oscillations and the presence of ferroin in addition modified the oscillations. Ferroin itself, however, was unable to induce second phase oscillations.

Results and Discussion

The values of the oscillation parameters like induction or transition period, total number of oscillations, total time of oscillations (excluding induction or transition period), time period of oscillation and amplitude and potential range of oscillation in both the first and second phases have been presented in Tables 1 and 2. In both the tables, the strength of the acid has been varied in set I and the catalyst varied (at two different acid strengths) in sets II and III. The effects of variation of concentration of acetone and amount of vanillin have been investigated in sets IV and V respectively. In

set VI, variation of the catalyst has been made when the system contains acetone also. Ferroin and Mn^{II} ions have been used as catalyst either separately or in combination. The serial number 23 represents the uncatalysed system. Some of the same combinations of the reactants and catalyst have been given different serial numbers (in place of same serial number) in the tables for convenience in comparing the observations. This has been indicated in the tables. Figs. 1–3 are the representative potentiometric traces under different experimental conditions.

Variation in acid strength (Set I) : The potentiometric traces for serial number 2 (Fig. 1(b)), when compared with

Fig. 1. Potential oscillation in vanillin- $KBrO_3$ - H_2SO_4 system: (a) with no catalyst and (b) with Mn^{II} ions as catalyst.

those for serial numbers 1 and 3 (traces not shown) show that excellent second phase oscillations with high amplitude take place at moderately high concentration of acid.

Variation in catalyst in absence of acetone (Sets II and III) : The serial number 23 (where no catalyst has been used) of the tables shows that in absence of an external catalyst, there is no sequential oscillation. Only a few high frequency oscillations take place within a few seconds with practi-

cally no induction period. Sets II and III indicate that Mn^{II} ions induce a sequential oscillation. Ferrioin alone, however, has practically no catalytic effect in this system. When both Mn^{II} ions and ferrioin are used in combination, the second phase oscillations become unusually broad. It appears that ferrioin modifies the catalytic effect of Mn^{II} ions and tries to make the second phase oscillations broad (vide Figs. 1 and 2).

Table 1. Oscillation characteristics of the B-Z system : KBrO₃-H₂SO₄-*p*-vanillin-Mn²⁺ and/or ferrioin

Vol. of reaction mixture = 30 ml, Temp. = 32 ± 1°, [KBrO₃] = 6.66 × 10⁻² M

Set no.	Sl. no.	[H ₂ SO ₄] N	[Mn ^{II}] × 10 ³ M	[Ferrioin] M	[Mn ^{II}] and [Ferrioin] M	Wt of <i>p</i> -vanillin g	Vol. of acetone ml	Induction period (s)		No. of oscillations		Total time of oscillations(s)*		Time-period of oscillations(s)		
								1st phase	2nd phase	1st phase	2nd phase	1st phase	2nd phase	1st phase	2nd phase	
I	1	1.6300	3.33	-	-	0.137	-	48	144	03	06	32	216	12	36	
	2	2.0490	3.33	-	-	0.137	-	Nil	168	04	12	32	432	08	32	
	3	2.1802	3.33	-	-	0.137	-	08	120	05	12	48	516	08	36	
II	4	2.0490	3.33	-	-	0.137	-	Nil	168	04	12	32	432	08	32	
	5	2.0490	-	8.3 × 10 ⁻⁵	-	0.137	-	08	-	03	-	32	-	08	-	
	6	2.0490	-	-	3.33 × 10 ⁻³	0.137	-	Nil	Nil (?)	04	04	32	1752	08	528	
and 8.30 × 10 ⁻⁵																
III	7	2.1802	3.33	-	-	0.137	-	08	120	05	12	48	516	08	36	
	8	2.1802	-	8.3 × 10 ⁻⁵	-	0.137	-	Nil	-	06	-	48	-	08	-	
	9	2.1802	-	-	3.33 × 10 ⁻³	0.137	-	Nil	Nil (?)	03	04	24	2184	08	816	
and 8.30 × 10 ⁻⁵																
IV	10	2.1802	3.33	-	-	0.137	3	Practically no oscillation								
	11	2.1802	3.33	-	-	0.137	1	Practically no oscillation								
	12	2.1802	3.33	-	-	0.082	1	Nil	636	02	64	12	2304	-	24	
	13	2.1802	3.33	-	-	0.082	2	Practically no oscillation								
V	14	2.1802	3.33	-	-	0.137	1	Practically no oscillation								
	15	2.1802	3.33	-	-	0.092	1	-	744	Nil	36	-	1104	-	12	
	(Very small)															
	16	2.1802	3.33	-	-	0.082	1	Nil	636	02	64	12	2304	-	24	
	17	2.1802	3.33	-	-	0.070	1	08	1080	02	>50	16	3160	08	Irregular oscillation	
	18	2.1802	3.33	-	-	0.059	1	12	2136	01	>32	-	5280	-	72	
19	2.1802	3.33	-	-	0.050	1	Practically no oscillation									
VI	20	2.1802	3.33	-	-	0.082	1	Nil	636	02	64	12	2304	-	24	
	21	2.1802	-	8.3 × 10 ⁻⁵	-	0.082	1	Nil	-	03	-	24	-	08	-	
	22	2.1802	-	-	3.33 × 10 ⁻³	0.082	1	Nil	1752	03	09	24	1008	08	108	
and 8.30 × 10 ⁻⁵																
No 23	2.1802	-	-	-	-	0.137	-	Nil	-	04	-	30	-	08	-	

catalyst

*Excluding induction period.

The following sl. nos. are same : 2 and 4; 3 and 7; 11 and 14; 12, 16 and 20. All oscillations are potentiometric only; only in sl. no. 22, later oscillations are visible (orange to light yellow) also.

Variation in acetone concentration (Set IV) : Set IV shows that in presence of high concentration of vanillin or acetone (using Mn^{II} ions as catalyst), practically no oscillation takes place. When their concentrations are low, excellent oscillations are observed (vide Tables 1 and 2 and Fig. 3(a)). It appears that the presence of excess of acetone in the system is not conducive to oscillations.

Fig. 2. Potential oscillation in vanillin-KBrO₃-H₂SO₄ system : (a) with ferriox as catalyst and (b) with Mn^{II} ions and ferriox both as catalyst.

Variation in the weight of vanillin (Set V) : The system was studied with different amounts of vanillin in presence of acetone and Mn^{II} ions as catalyst. In case of high or low concentration of vanillin, there was practically no oscillation. With intermediate concentration of vanillin, a large number of oscillations were observed and the oscillations continued for a long time. The oscillations, however, were mostly of low amplitude (vide Tables 1 and 2 and Fig. 3(a)).

Variation in catalyst in presence of acetone (Set VI) : When Mn^{II} ions were used as catalyst, very good oscillations were obtained in the second phase and the oscillations continued for a long time. With ferriox, however, there was no second phase oscillation. With a combination of the above catalysts, very low amplitude second phase oscillations were observed and the oscillations were visible also (orange to light yellow). Ferriox, however, had a broadening effect on the potentiometric traces. In all cases, a few high frequency oscillations occurred in the first phase (vide Figs. 1-3).

Characteristics of the oscillations (vide Tables 1 and 2). First phase or initial oscillations : (a) Induction period

is nil or practically nil. (b) Oscillations are only a few in number (2-6). (c) Oscillations are very quick, i.e. of high frequency; time-period is only about 10 s or less. (d) Oscillations continue for about 1 min or less (12-50 s). (e) The amplitude of oscillation is moderately large and varies from about 20 to 200 mV under different experimental conditions. (f) Oscillations occur even in the absence of a catalyst and are not appreciably influenced by a catalyst. (g) The oscillations are only potentiometric and not visible. (h) The oscillations stop suddenly.

Fig. 3. Potential oscillation in vanillin-KBrO₃-H₂SO₄-acetone system : (a) with Mn^{II} ions as catalyst and (b) with Mn^{II} ions and ferriox both as catalyst.

Second phase oscillations : (a) Induction period or transition period varies from about 2 to 35 min. (b) The number of oscillations may be small or large (about 4 to 65). The number is large specially in presence of acetone. (c) The oscillation periods may vary from about 0.5 to 14 min. The long period oscillations, i.e. broad oscillations are obtained when both Mn^{II} ions and ferriox are used as catalysts. (d) The oscillations may continue for a few minutes in some cases or beyond 1.5 h in some other cases. In presence of acetone, oscillations continue for a long time. (e) The amplitude of potential oscillation varies from about 10 to 310 mV. (f) The oscillations are induced by catalysts like Mn^{II} ions, or Mn^{II} ions and ferriox in combination, but not in presence of ferriox alone. (g) The oscillations are

mostly potentiometric. They are also visible only in a few cases. (h) The oscillations generally die down gradually. With Mn^{II} ions as catalyst in absence of acetone, the oscillations stop suddenly.

Mechanism : The broad mechanism of B-Z chemical oscillation has been worked out by Field, Körös and Noyes (FKN mechanism)⁴. Various models like Oregonator etc. have been proposed. In the present system, it is likely that vanillin is oxidised by bromate ions to vanillic acid and by

bromination some amount of 5-bromovanillin is formed. Due to both oxidation and bromination, 5-bromovanillic acid is also expected. When the system contains acetone also, monobromoacetone will be formed in addition.

The previous workers³ got sequential oscillations using mixed substrate systems. The first phase oscillations were due to one substrate and later oscillations were due to other substrates in the system. In the present studies, only one substrate, namely, vanillin has been used in most of the runs.

Table 2. Potential changes of B-Z system : $KBrO_3-H_2SO_4-p$ -vanillin Mn^{II} and/or ferroin

Set no.	Sl. no.	(mV) Amplitude*		Potential range (V)		Comment
		1st phase	2nd phase	1st phase	2nd phase	
I	1	30	40	0.58-0.61	0.55-0.59	Both 1st and 2nd phase oscillations are of small amplitude
	2	180	180	0.65-0.83	0.65-0.83	Both oscillations are pronounced and suddenly die down. Fig. 1(b)
	3	20	50	0.62-0.64	0.59-0.64	2nd phase oscillations have larger amplitude
II	4	180	180	0.65-0.83	0.65-0.83	Same as sl. no. 2
	5	180	-	0.64-0.82	-	No 2nd phase oscillation; 1st phase oscillations have large amplitude. Fig. 2(a)
	6	200	280	0.64-0.84	0.63-0.91	Both oscillations have large amplitude. 2nd phase oscillations are very broad. Fig. 2(b)
III	7	20	50	0.62-0.64	0.59-0.64	Same as sl. no. 3
	8	170	-	0.64-0.81	-	1st phase oscillations have large amplitude; no 2nd phase oscillation
	9	170	310	0.64-0.81	0.55-0.86	Both 1st and 2nd phase oscillations have large amplitude; 2nd phase oscillations are very broad
IV	10	-	-	-	-	Practically no oscillation
	11	-	-	-	-	Practically no oscillation
	12	70	40	0.59-0.66	0.44-0.48	Both oscillations have small amplitude; amplitude of 2nd phase oscillation decreases gradually. Fig. 3(a)
V	13	-	-	-	-	Practically no oscillation
	14	-	-	-	-	Same as sl. no. 11
	15	-	10	-	0.27-0.28	No 1st phase oscillation; 2nd phase oscillations are of very small amplitude
	16	70	40	0.59-0.66	0.44-0.48	Same as sl. no. 12
	17	30	20	0.415-0.445	0.26-0.28	Both oscillations are of small amplitude
	18	70	20	0.42-0.49	0.30-0.32	Only one oscillation in 1st phase; 2nd phase oscillations have small amplitude
VI	19	-	-	-	-	Practically no oscillation
	20	70	40	0.59-0.66	0.44-0.48	Same as sl. no. 12
	21	40	-	0.55-0.59	-	No oscillation in 2nd phase
	22	60	10	0.55-0.61	0.40-0.41	1st phase oscillations potentiometric only 2nd phase oscillations both potentiometric and visible. Fig. 3(b)
No catalyst	23	160	-	0.64-0.80	-	Quick potential oscillation in 1st phase only Fig. 1(a)

*Approximate values in the beginning.

The following serial nos. are same : 2 and 4; 3 and 7; 11 and 14; 12, 16 and 20.

The initial very quick oscillations are perhaps due to vanillin itself as it is very easily oxidised and later oscillations after a break are probably due to its oxidation/bromination products. The system is an example of a coupled oscillation in which species A, which is responsible for oscillations, produces another species B, which also generates oscillations after a pause.

In some of the runs, acetone has been used along with vanillin. In these cases, the number of oscillations and total time of oscillation increase enormously (Table 1). Acetone, however, does not oscillate alone at ordinary temperature though it is a bromine scavenger and a reductant. As the rate of its oxidation is slow, and additional organic or inorganic reductant is generally necessary⁵. In the present case when both vanillin and acetone are present, the system becomes a smooth homogeneous mixed substrate system and acetone modifies the second phase oscillations remarkably. In this phase, the oscillation parameters, viz. induction period, number of oscillations and total time of oscillation have higher values in presence of acetone indicating a slower rate of reaction. On the other hand, in the first phase of oscillations, the number of oscillations and total time of oscillation slightly decrease in its presence indicating a slight increase in reaction rate. Thus the behaviour is opposite for the two phases of oscillation. Moreover, the change in polarity of the medium is only slight as one changes the medium from water to aqueous acetone (3.3% acetone, v/v). It is difficult to come to a conclusion whether the polarity of the medium has any role in this case.

Experimental

To a weighed amount of *p*-vanillin (Ranbaxy Laboratories, L.R.) requisite quantities of moderately strong sulphuric acid, manganous sulphate (Sarabhai M. Chemicals, G.R.) solution (and/or ferroin), water, acetone (s.d.fine chemicals, A.R.) and potassium bromate (Sarabhai M. Chemicals, G.R.) solution were added such that the concentrations shown in Table 1 were the concentrations in

reaction medium at the start. The reaction was triggered by the addition of the last reagent. No reagent was added any further so that the system was a closed one in the thermodynamic sense and it worked in batch mode. The reaction mixture was slowly stirred at a fixed rate with the help of a magnetic stirrer. The solution was homogeneous only when acetone also was present. A bright platinum electrode was put in the reaction mixture and coupled with a saturated calomel electrode (reference electrode) through ammonium nitrate salt-bridge. The two electrodes were connected to a x-t strip chart recorder and the potential oscillations were recorded.

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References

1. B. P. Belousov, "1958 Collection of Abstracts on Radiation Medicine", Medgiz, Moscow, 1959, p. 145; A. M. Zhabotinskii, *Biofizika*, 1964, 9, 306; "Oscillations and Travelling Waves in Chemical Systems", eds. R. J. Field and M. Burger, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1985.
2. P. V. Lalitha and R. Ramaswamy, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1992, 47, 133.
3. R. J. Kaner and I. R. Epstein, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 100, 4073; E. J. Heilweil, M. J. Henchman and I. R. Epstein, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 101, 3698; R. P. Rastogi, I. Das and A. Sharma, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1989, 85, 2011; P. K. Srivastava, Y. Mori and I. Hanazaki, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, 95, 1636; L. Adamcikova and P. Sevcik, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1995, 56, 137; H. Li and X. Huang, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1996, 255, 137; H. Li, R. Jin, W. Dai and J. Deng, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1997, 274, 41.
4. R. J. Field, E. Körös and R. M. Noyes, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 94, 8649.
5. R. P. Rastogi and G. P. Misra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, 29, 1205.